

THE ROLE OF SPIRITUAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада ёшларнинг ҳар томонлама баркамол инсонлар бўлиб вояга етишлари мамлакатнинг келгуси барқарор тараққиётида муҳим аҳамият касб этиши атрофлича тадқиқ этилган. Ўз навбатида ёш авлоднинг камол топишида миллий қадриятлар, маънавий мерос дурдоналари, хусусан, миллий эпосимизнинг аҳамияти хусусида фикр юритилган.

Калит сўзлар: ёшлар камолоти, миллий қадриятлар, маънавий мерос, эпос, фольклор, дostonлар, бахшилар, маънавият булоғи, эстетик мезонлар, глобаллашув.

Аннотация: В данной статье тот факт, что молодые люди вырастают всесторонне развитыми людьми, важен для будущего устойчивого развития страны. В свою очередь, обсуждалось значение национальных ценностей, шедевров духовного наследия, особенно нашего национального эпоса в развитии молодого поколения.

Ключевые слова: зрелость молодежи, национальные ценности, духовное наследие, эпос, фольклор, эпосы, бахши, источник духовности, эстетические критерии, глобализация.

Annotation: In this article, the fact that young people grow up to be comprehensively developed people is important for the future sustainable development of the country. In turn, the importance of national values, masterpieces of spiritual heritage, especially our national epic in the development of the younger generation, was discussed.

Key words: maturity of youth, national values, spiritual heritage, epos, folklore, epics, gifts, source of spirituality, aesthetic criteria, globalization.

The education of young people who are the masters of the country's future, mature people in all respects, is one of the priorities of the social policy implemented in our country. After all, concern for the development of the country, the search for a bright future begins with concern for today's youth. No wonder they say that today is responsible for tomorrow.

The development of young people as physically healthy, mentally mature and thinking individuals depends on a number of important aspects. The intended goal can be achieved only with strict adherence to each of these aspects. One of such important aspects is the deep introduction into the hearts and minds of the younger generation of our national values, spiritual heritage, traditions and customs that have been formed and improved over the centuries. After all, the influence of the established historical and cultural traditions on the maturation of the younger generation, on familiarization with the beauties of spiritual life is very great. A generation that does not use the culture of its people and does not feed on it directly will never become a mature person, such as in the brochure.

The spiritual maturity of young people, their growing up smart, moral, faithful, conscientious, feeling the fate of the country and the pain of the people with their hearts are masterpieces of our spiritual heritage - the epic heritage of our people. is of great importance.

This huge treasure with a centuries-old history has served as an invaluable resource for educating young people in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people, and today perfectly fulfills this task.

After all, the "Epic" has many lessons. By reading and listening to the epic, one can understand the essence of the past, present and future."¹ After all, the ideas of national liberation, patriotism, heroism, courage, friendship, honesty, love and loyalty sung in folk epics are inexhaustible spiritual food for all of us. But, unfortunately, on the one hand, due to globalization, the speed of time, and on the other hand, due to the variety of entertainment provided by information and communication technologies, which are incomparably developing, our youth are increasingly moving away from this priceless treasure.

Fewer and fewer of our youth are turning to this source of spirituality. This is not a good sign, and since we want our youth to grow smoothly, we should not look at this situation indifferently. To introduce them to the epic, one of the masterpieces of the thought of our ancestors, to encourage them to quench their spiritual thirst from this spiritual awakening is an urgent task for adults, especially teachers.

"In other words, the study of folklore means the study of everyday life, customs, traditions, history, present and future, thoughts and mentality of people. Because it reflects the identity of the nation, the principles of self-expression, a long-term lifestyle and worldview"².

According to experts, it is possible to find out how ancient the history of a people is, how strong its spirituality is, from its epic. Looking at the number and content of our national epic, we feel endless pride – how ancient our history is, how high our spirituality is. To convey the essence of this greatness to the youth is a moral, educational, pedagogical duty and task. Undoubtedly, an important step in this is the study of the secrets of the art of bakhshi. Bakhshilik is a wonderful art that has been passed down from generation to generation for several years. Uzbek Bakhshi are unique artists in the history of mankind who have preserved the traditions of oral epic and classical epic in live performance until the XXI century.

Uzbek Bakhshi are the owners of divine abilities. He preserved the traditions of the past in the memory of every Bakshi, passed them from generation to generation and enriched and updated them every time during the performance.

Bakhshi with epic knowledge and outstanding memory continued performing art, which they learned from their teachers, according to certain patterns. The Uzbek epic, which has an ancient tradition, developed in various directions, famous epic schools were formed. Our folklore, which is the product of rich artistic traditions, embodies dreams, noble thoughts, a unique way of life and moral views of our people. Therefore, folklore works are not only a mirror reflecting the spiritual appearance of our people, but also one of the important and powerful means of folk education.

¹ Shomirza Turdimov, Uchmas sira donish chirogi. "Tafakkur", 2015 year, №1. – S.8.

² Jabbor Eshonkul. "Sim-sim xazinasi". "Tafakkur", 2001 year, №2, P.47.

«That's why our people have loved to learn, listen, perform and create an epic since time immemorial. Because epics are closely connected with the life of the people, they embody human dreams, moral and aesthetic views, high ideals of heroism and patriotism».

These national and universal values, sung in epics, are important today. After all, the heroes sung in folk epics serve as high ideals in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, in their growing up as brave, brave and honest people.³

Especially in the current era, when technological development is growing at an unprecedented level, the strengthening of technocratic views, admiration for technical achievements, being captured by the virtual world, alienation from society and protection from licentiousness, cruelty and immorality, spreading in the form of "mass culture", national values are also used in preserving identity and protecting humanity, in particular in particular, the need for the educational value of folklore has increased.

This situation is visible not only in our country, but even on a global scale, it is clear that in world literature and world cinema, the principle of turning to folklore and finding strength in the educational power of folklore is growing. After all, people who are tired of lies and hypocrisy want to return to the simplicity and sincerity inherent in the layers of myth and folklore.

There is no nation that does not want its children to grow up to be perfect people. Therefore, human virtues are the main theme of literature and art of all peoples. In the same way, the idea of humanity is glorified in Uzbek folk epics, and real people are glorified in centuries-old legends and legends, folk epics.

«Children like Gorogly, sons like Alpomish, daughters like Barchinoy, matured in all aspects of the nation, have reached this level thanks to their commitment to the values of the country to which they belong, education, faith, trust, etc.

Therefore, it is impossible to achieve perfection without following the teachings of the ancestors and the lessons learned from their life experience».⁴

At its core, folk art is a process that is always being updated, living, improving, continuously developing. It cannot be otherwise in our world of movement and change. Similarly, it is impossible to find any ritual or folklore work created and preserved to this day without any changes.

Each epoch, each generation has made changes to a number of ancestral values based on its artistic and aesthetic criteria. Therefore, experts describe folklore as a creation in constant motion.

Today, along with all genres of folklore, the performance of the epic has also changed. Folklore moves to a new form of life, that is, folklore moves from public performance to the stage, as a result of which it adapts to the requirements of the stage. Because it takes time.

Another distinctive feature of folklore is that it shows the living language of the people in all its richness, charm and diversity.

³ Maxfuza Raxmonova. Uzbekiston nomoddiy madaniy merosi: xalk dostonlari, xalk tomosha san'ati, xalk uyinlari. Karshi, "Nasaf" NMIU, 2022, - P.28.

⁴ Abdiolim Ergashev. Xalk dostonlarida barkamol inson timsoli. "Milliy istiklol va shaxs kamoloti", Karshi, "Nasaf", 2002 year.. - P. 260.

She will not fail to please a person with her loose thoughts, meaningless expressions, disorderly jokes, exaggerations and comparisons. Until now, epic art has been performed only live, and each performer enriched it with his skill, talent, ingenuity, eloquence.

Due to globalization, integration of cultures, scientific and technological progress, the appeal to folklore is an important factor in preserving the charm of our language against the background of increasing external influences on the native language.

In conclusion, I want to say that the rich and unique folklore works of our people, especially epics, teach all of us, especially the younger generation, the virtues of humanity. Because it teaches people to be just and righteous, to defend their country, ancestral fortress, friends, honor and sacred graves of their ancestors from any aggression, therefore it is very important to read and study them at all times, including today.

References:

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